

PLC BASED PID SPEED CONTROL SYSTEM OF INDUCTION MOTOR

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Abstract

A Programmable Logic Controller grounded control system of Induction motor is designed using commensurable-integral- outgrowth (PID) regulator. The control circle feedback medium regulator is extensively used in Artificial control system. The regulator parameters ensuring sluggish response at each reference speed are obtained using an optimization technique. As a result, the induction motor's performance is unaffected by disturbances because the regulator circular response stability is steadily increased by the proposed technique.

Keywords: Programmable Logic Controller, Induction Motor, MATLAB/Simulink, PWM Subsystem, Motor, PID Controller.

1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter includes the introduction to this project which gives a brief information how this project uses induction motor and PLC in PID controller along with the simulation results.

1.1. Induction Motor

A typical type of AC electrical engine, which is also referred as an associative asynchronous motor. In induction motor, to produce the electrical flow required to generate force in the rotor, the stator coil winding's spinning attractive field is utilised as a field. The rotor of associate time period engine is a squirrel confine rotor or wound kind rotor.

Three-stage squirrel-confine time period engines are generally utilised as fashionable drives since they're self-beginning, dependable and economical. Single-stage time period engines are utilised generally for minor burdens, as an example, domestic devices like fans.

Though typically utilised in fixed- speed administration Induction motor, are more and more being utilised with variable-frequency drives (VFD) in issue speed administration.

1.2 Programmable Logic Controller (Plc)

A modern, advanced PC which has been reinforced and adjusted as a measure of assembly processes, that is sequential construction systems, mechanical equipment's, and other movement which demands higher dependability, programmable simplicity, and cycle issue determination is called a programmable logic controller (PLC).

They may be designed for a variety of purposes, including sophisticated and basic Input/Output, expanded temperature levels, resistance to noise produced by electrical equipment's, and defense against fluctuation and shock. Projects that regulate machine activity frequently make use of unpredictable or battery-operated memory.

In order to replace hard-wired hand-off reasoning frameworks, Programmable Logic Controller's initially appeared in automotive sector that offer's adaptable, rudimentary, efficiently programmable regulators etc. And also, Programmable Logic Controller gained widespread acceptance as highly efficient mechanical regulators suitable for difficult circumstances.

2. IDENTIFICATION OF THE PROBLEM

The project solves the matter of varied speed of the induction motor in industries due to the excess load on the conveyer belt. the load will increase on the conveyer belt the speed decreases that makes the method terribly slow and time taking inflicting heaps of issues to the industries. We are victimization PLC with pelvic inflammatory disease controllers to take care of a continuing speed of the induction motor victimization V/f technique so it will resolve the matter of varied speed of the motor no matter the load in sugar, oil industries.

Figure 2.1: Conveyor Belt Carrying Sugar Gunny Bags

2.1 Methodology

2.1.1 Voltage/Frequency Control Method

Voltage/Frequency control is a control technique that ensures the output voltage is proportional to the frequency produced. It prevents weak magnetic and magnetic saturation phenomena from happening by maintaining a constant motor flux.

2.1.2 Control Principle

The V/F control principle involves supplying generator frequency into a circuit referred to as a voltage-control generator. It is a voltage-dependent capacitance, meaning that when the voltage is altered, its capability can also change.

This change in capability may result in changes in the oscillated frequency, which results in the changeable frequency. This regulated frequency is used to alter the frequency of the output voltage to produce speed changes for the controlled electrical motors.

3. PROJECT FRAMEWORK

3.1 Block Diagram

The Block diagram of Programmable Logic Controller based PID speed control system is given below. The various components in the control system and their working are explained in the following section.

Figure 3.1: Block Diagram Of Programmable Logic Controller Based PID Speed Control System Of Induction Motor

3.2 Working

The reference speed is selected using PLC logo software and fed to the PID controller. The controller output produces the required frequency for the generation of sinusoidal signal. The frequency of this sinusoidal signal corresponds to the frequency of the voltage signal supplied to the PWM block, and the amplitude of this sinusoidal signal refers to the amplitude of the voltage signal. The PWM block generates six gate drives required for six MOSFET's. The DC voltage of 700V is applied to the inverter circuit which produces three phase AC voltage. Induction motor speed is detected using a tachogenerator and supplied back to the PID controller after three phase AC voltage has been supplied to the motor. For different reference speeds, the performance of the motor is analysed.

4. SIMULATION, RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

Utilizing MATLAB/Simulink, the proposed control system is simulated. The Simulink model and its working is discussed in this chapter. Finally, the simulation results are analysed.

4.1 Simulink Model

Utilizing MATLAB/Simulink, the speed control of a three-phase induction motor is simulated. In given below Figure, the Simulink model is displayed. Modelling the induction motor in an appropriate dq standard frame. An internal neutral point is connected by a wye to both the rotor and stator windings.

The inverter used here is the six switch three phase inverter. The speed setting is given here as the automatic switch from PLC. The reference speed is the set point here. The speeds set here are 500, 1000, 1100, 1300 and 1500 RPM. If a switch in the PLC is pressed the motor has to operate at the set speed.

The control output from the PID controller is provided to the sine wave generator block where a three-phase sinusoidal frequency signal is generated. Further the signal is fed to PWM block which produces control signals to trigger the MOSFET'S.

The DC supply is applied to the MOSFET's, and this inverter circuit converts DC voltage to three phase Alternating Current voltage. The AC voltage (440 V) is applied to the induction motor. A scope is used to measure the rotor angle, rotor speed, and electromagnetic torque.

Figure 4.1: Simulink Model Of The Proposed Control System

4.2 Pwm Subsystem Model

The subsystem model of PWM block is shown in figure 4.2. Here the input is three phase balanced signal and it is converted to six gate drive signals.

Figure 4.2: PWM Subsystem Model

4.3 Plc System

The ladder logic used in the system is covered in the subsection as following.

4.3.1 Ladder Diagram

The ladder diagram is described in figure.

Figure 4.3.1: Ladder Logic

4.4 Ideal Condition Of Motor Control

The ideal condition of motor implies that it is not operating. Here the start contact is kept normally open. This condition is represented in figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Ideal Condition Of Motor Control

4.5 Starting Operation Of Motor

When I1 switch present at the toggle bar, is pressed the start contact gets closed. This eventually triggers the start relay Q7. This process is described in figure.

Figure 4.5: Starting Operation Of The Relay

4.5.1 Motor Operation At 500 Rpm

As the start relay Q7 is turned on, the I2 contact is closed by just pressing on the I2 switch present at the toggle bar. As a result, Q1 relay is enabled and it triggers the speed as 500 RPM. The following figure describes the operation.

Figure 4.5.1: Motor Operation at 500 rpm

4.5.2 Motor Operation At 1000 Rpm

Now the I2 switch is released and the I3 contact is closed by just pressing on the I3 switch present at the toggle bar. As a result, Q2 relay is enabled and it triggers the speed as 1000 RPM. The following figure describes the operation.

Figure 4.5.2: Speed at 1000rpm

4.6 Simulation Results

The speed is controlled here by the switches of PLC as there is no physical device of PLC present. The simulation is done using PLC as a switching device and the ladder diagram is drawn for controlling the set point.

4.6.1 Balanced Signal Waveform

The output of Sine wave generator is a three-phase balanced signal. The waveform of this balanced signal is shown in figure.

Figure 4.6.1: Three Phase Balanced Sinusoidal Signal

4.6.2 Supply Current And Voltage Waveforms

The inverter circuit's output is given to VI measurement block where in the voltage and current are measured and the waveforms are obtained using a scope. The voltage waveform clearly shows that the three-phase voltage's peak value is 600 and that the induction motor receives the RMS value of this voltage. The below figure shows the waveform between I and V.

Figure 4.6.2: Supply Current And Voltage Waveforms

4.6.3 Motor Speed And Torque Waveforms

During the initial operation, the motor speed oscillates about the reference speed. From the speed curve, it can be seen that when the reference speed is increased periodically, the oscillations are damped. Thus, at higher speeds the error is minimized by the PID controller. The rotor angle curve is also shown in figure.

5. CONCLUSION

The proposed control system was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink and the PLC logic was implemented in the system. The motor speed was observed to be oscillating for a certain period when the reference speed was set at 500 rpm. Further, as the reference speed was increased, the oscillations in the speed of induction motor were mitigated and the motor operated in constant torque mode. Thus, the variation in the frequency was achieved by changing the reference speed with the help of PLC logo software and the motor performance was analysed in the MATLAB/Simulink.

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